
TEACHERS' SUPPORT SERVICES AS PREDICTORS OF TEACHERS' JOB COMMITMENT IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ANAMBRA STATE

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Abstract

The study examined teachers' support services as predictors of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Two research questions guided the study and two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study was a correlational research design. The population of the study comprised 6,598 teachers in the 267 public secondary schools from the six Education Zones in Anambra State. The sample of 330 teachers (that is, 5% of teachers' population) was used for the study. Multistage sampling techniques comprising of proportionate stratified and simple random sampling technique was used for the study. Teachers' Support Services Questionnaire (TSSQ) and Teachers' Job Commitment Questionnaire (TJCQ) were used for data collection. The instruments were subjected to face and construct validation. Face validation was done by three experts while construct validation was carried out with Principal Component Analysis approach. The reliability of the instrument was done using Cronbach Alpha technique and the average coefficient values of 0.81 for TSSQ and 0.86 for TJCQ are considered highly reliable and suitable for the study. Simple regression analysis was used for the study. The study revealed that fringe benefits ($r=0.518$ $p=0.000$) and recognition ($r=0.504$ $p=0.000$) positively and significantly predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Based on the findings, the study recommended among others that Management and administrators of public secondary schools in Anambra State should as much as possible provide attractive and handy fringe benefits to create sense of loyalty and boost teachers' decisions to stay longer with their schools.

Keywords: Teachers, Support Services, Job Commitment

Introduction

Teachers at all levels of education are the foundation and bedrock of quality education in the society. Teachers are very important in any education system as no proper education can ever be achieved without adequately trained and motivated teachers. Teachers are the pillars of the society who help students to grow and shoulder the responsibility of nation building. Teachers are indeed the nation's human capital, and every effort needs to be made to ensure improvement in their job commitment. Job commitment can be seen as the process through which people become willing to give their loyalty and energy to a particular social system. Teachers' job commitment refers to teachers' emotional attachment or bond to their job and the school. It can also be seen as the level of allegiance teachers feel for their job.

Teachers' job commitment is one of the most essential elements that could facilitate the effective teaching required to enhance the academic achievement of students in schools. As such, teachers with high level of commitment could make a difference to teaching and learning in the school system. It is associated with creating an effective learning environment in which students enhance their abilities for greater performance. Obiekwe (2019) described teachers' job commitment as teachers' identification with and involvement in a particular school. This commitment can be characterized by a strong personal belief in and acceptance of the school goals and values, a desire to exert oneself for the betterment of the school, and a strong will to remain with the school. Umezulike *et al.* (2024) defined teachers' job commitment as the psychological identification of the individual teacher with the school and the intention of that teacher to maintain his membership of the school, and show all personal interest. High level of teachers' commitment is essential for school success. Teachers with high level of commitment view themselves as integral part of the school, what threatens the school endangers them as well, they do their best to perform their duties better, and work for the school as if it belongs to them (Aminu *et al.*, 2023). In contrast, teachers with low level of commitment are less faithful to the school, view themselves as outsiders and are more concerned with personal success than with the success of the school as a whole.

Teachers' job commitment is an internal force that comes from within an individual. This is true because people differ in what motivates them and what they are seeking from work. However, unless people feel they are valued and treated fairly in an organization, they may not be intellectually and emotionally committed or motivated to willingly give their best. This implies that, before teachers can be committed to their teaching profession, they must be willing to make intense efforts for goal achievement of their school organizations which they have strong desire to remain members of the organisation.

Teachers who are committed to their job are more enthusiastic and interested in devoting more energy and time to teach students in a manner that would improve their academic achievement. Committed teachers are always willing to contribute their ideas and efforts to the pursuit of school goals of promoting effective teaching and learning. Kaegon and Okere (2023) maintained that teachers with positive perception about their teaching role would be willing to accept the goals and values of their schools easily and they would be highly committed in teaching the students to enable them excel in their academic pursuits. Committed teachers show high levels of dedication to teaching and learning and they may avoid frequent absenteeism from school and display positive attitude towards their teaching responsibilities (Umezulike *et al.*, 2024). Having committed teachers in the school system is beneficial in the sense that it would produce positive results especially in the area of high academic achievement by students. A school that has committed teachers has the highest

possibility being successful academically because committed teachers are sometimes more productive in promoting effective and efficient teaching services in the school system.

In this study, teachers' job commitment refers to teachers' psychological bond to the school, including a sense of job involvement, loyalty and a belief in the values of the school. The commitment of teachers depends on their motivation, morale and job satisfaction. This implies that teachers' job commitment is an important phenomenon for all secondary school teachers, their employers and students at large. For the success of any organization, committed human resources are considered as the most important assets of an organization. Thus, teachers' job commitment is an indicator of a teacher's loyalty, professional attachment and job pleasure. It tends to reflect the level of fulfillment; an individual feel from his nature of work and organizational attachment. For optimal teachers' job commitment in the school, their perception of support services in the school is crucial. Teachers' support services are collection of processes or activities that are designed for teachers to ensure the operational efficiency of their service delivery in schools.

Teachers' support services are those services provided to facilitate the implementation of educational policies, attainment of educational goals and promote the effectiveness of the educational system. They are services that can promote teachers' effectiveness in the discharge of their professional responsibilities and also improve students' learning. Sunoma *et al.* (2022) described support services as those specialized functions that are not typically educational themselves but are aimed at improving teaching and learning in a particular educational system. Therefore, support services are provided to help teachers in schools to be effective and improve upon teaching and learning. They include all human and other resources that provide support to teachers and learners as well as other aspects of the education system. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2014) identified the aims of educational support services to include: to enhance teaching and improve the competence of teachers, provide conducive school environment for learning, make learning experiences realistic and more meaningful to the learners, make education more cost effective and to promote in-service education for teachers.

Support services include those services provided by both professionals and the para-professionals to schools to address diverse learning skills and problems of the students. These services when managed well support the teaching and learning process by addressing the underlying issues such as academic behavioural lapses and mental health problems that challenge and bar effective teaching and learning. Educational support services refer to wide range of services offered to both students and teachers to help them discover their individual academic skills and to become self-sufficient, independent, life-long learners. The personnel who offer these services comprise of a broad range of professionals in guidance/counsellors, facilitators who help teachers develop themselves professionally, librarians and technicians/technologists (Chukwueze, 2023). They work as an integrated team within network of schools, focusing on the provision of group-based and individual support, workforce capacity building and provision of specialized services. Thus, management of support services for teachers refers to the planning, coordination, direction, channeling and organization of educational resources provided to aid in the smooth running of the school (Zulkiflee *et al.*, 2023). Zulkiflee *et al.* (2023) further noted teachers' support services to include transportation assistance, day care expenses, clothes, books and supplies, good work environment, academic advising, advocacy, course fees, in-service training, license and testing fees or other items that are required for teachers to participate in education. These resources are managed against theft, damage and sustainability.

In this study, teachers' support services are processes or activities that schools are engaged to or use for teachers to execute a core programme or functions that enhance and improve teachers' job commitment in the schools. Teachers' support services also refer to a wide range of services that are designed to assist teachers in meeting their needs and achieving their goals. In this study, emphasis was based on three teachers' support services including: fringe benefits, recognition, information and communication technology (ICT) support services.

Teachers' fringe benefits are additional compensation provided to teachers that is not directly related with their salary or wages for the performance of a specific service. Some fringe benefits such as social security and health insurance are required by law, while others are voluntarily provided by the employer. Examples of optional fringe benefits include free breakfast and lunch, employee stock options, transportation benefits, retirement planning services, childcare, and education assistance, among others. Agah and Yakubu (2024) described fringe benefits as a form of pay, often from employers to employees, and considered compensation for services beyond the employees' normal rate of pay. It is a collection of various benefits provided by an employer which are exempt from taxation as long as certain conditions are met. They are benefits or compensation given to employees in addition to wages or salaries or compensation beyond a regular salary or wage with monetary value such as pension, health insurance coverage, and life insurance coverage (Agah & Yakubu, 2024). They can be made in the form of property, services, cash, or cash equivalents (Zulkiflee *et al.*, 2023). Cash equivalents are things that can be turned into cash fairly quickly, such as savings bonds. Teachers' fringe benefits in this study are regarded as the collection of various benefits provided by an employer, which are exempted from taxation as long as certain conditions are met. Thus, teachers' fringe benefits vary according to schools and can come in different forms like medical and dental insurance, use of a company's car, housing allowance, educational assistance, vacation pay, sick pay, meals and employees' discounts among others. Teachers' fringe benefits can also come in form of praise, rewards and recognition.

Recognition occurs when school principals share teachers' good work and achievement with them and even with extended audience. Mackenzie and Nwafor (2019) noted that recognition is good indications that the behaviour of the teacher is valued. They further noted that it is common in a workplace for employers to get more of the employees' behaviour they recognise and appreciate. They make teachers to fulfill task and their dreams. They are capable of eliciting good work performance needed to maintain commitment in the school. A principal's quick feedback after observing a teacher teach good lesson, after assessing his/her school records or consistently being punctual to school, will help school administrators maintain what can be described as "psychological contract". Teachers' recognitions can be as candid as a pat-on-the-back and a genuine compliment. It can also be as simple as a 'thank you', praises, applause or a friendly greeting at work (Kaegon & Okeke, 2023). Recognition could improve workers' commitment in an organization.

However, in Nigeria today, Anambra State inclusive, the general perception is that there is a general trend of low commitment of teachers to their job as evidenced from their minimal devotion and dedication to teaching which has resulted to poor academic performance among the students around the States in Nigeria including Anambra State (Obiekwe *et al.*, 2024). Stories of teachers' incompetence such as absenteeism, nonchalant attitude, low turnover in work place, lateness to class, inefficiency and ineffectiveness are raised in all the components of the society and one of the reasons adduced for these

educational disloyalty practices may be their perception of their principals' support services. Since it is believed that teachers' perception of their schools' support services may prevent them from getting involved in their job, thereby eroding educational objectives.

In public secondary schools in Anambra State, it is unfortunate that most secondary school teachers are subjected to work under conditions where there is few or no office facilities; where classrooms are overcrowded with students; where promotion, payment of salaries, fringe benefits and other entitlements are unduly delayed; where teachers are inadequately motivated and where there is inadequate provision for support services, they will be less committed and unsatisfied to give their best at work to promote performance as well as enhance moral development of their students. Working under such deplorable conditions, create a negative school climate in which the morale of teachers could be low. This could result in lack of commitment to work among teachers. It is on this background that the researcher sought to investigate teachers' support services as predictors of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Statement of the Problem

In Anambra State, teachers' job commitment seems not to be high and is declining in spite of the high expectations the society places on the teachers as professionals. It therefore appears teachers devote minimal commitment to their legitimate duties which seem to undermine the achievement of qualitative education. The researcher's interaction with some teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State seems to give the impression that they are not taking their jobs seriously. Some of them complain that their principals do not stimulate their innovative and creative ability by failing to encourage them to approach problems in new ways in order to achieve better results. This has resulted to some teachers exhibiting non-chalant attitude to work, some come late to school, some undertake unauthorized movement from school, some use the official hours for their private businesses, while some do not exhibit zeal in performing assigned responsibilities. Due to this, many schools seem not to be living up to the expected standard due to low level of commitment from teachers to school activities. This may likely have a negative impact on their commitment. This study therefore examined teachers' support services as predictors of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to examine teachers' support services as predictors of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to determine how:

1. Fringe benefits predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Recognition predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. How does fringe benefits predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. What is the predictive value of recognition on teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Fringe benefits do not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Recognition does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Methods

A correlational research design was adopted for the study. The study was carried out in Anambra State, Nigeria. Anambra State is one of the five States in South-East, Nigeria. The reason for using Anambra State as the area of study is as a result of the fact that Anambra State is educationally advantaged. Thus, the observable poor commitment of teachers such as nonchalant attitude towards teaching, lack of commitment among teachers, problem of attrition in teaching, lack of motivation and unethical behaviour of some teachers in public secondary schools prompted the researcher to examine how teachers' support services predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The population of 6,598 teachers in the 267 public secondary schools from the six education zones in Anambra State was used for the study. The sample of 330 teachers was used for the study. Multistage sampling techniques comprising of proportionate stratified and simple random sampling technique was used for the study. Proportionate stratified random sampling technique was used to divide the public secondary schools into six strata according to education zones and seven schools were drawn from each stratum in each education zone for good representation, making a total of 42 schools. Simple random sampling technique was used to draw 330 teachers for the study.

Two structured instruments were used for data collection titled 'Teachers' Support Services Questionnaire (TSSQ) and Teachers' Job Commitment Questionnaire (TJCQ).' The instruments are structured in three sections namely A, B and C. Section A deals with the personal data of the respondents, while section B and C deals with TSSQ and TJCQ. Teachers' Support Services Questionnaire (TSSQ) as structured by the researcher measured teachers' support services in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The instrument TSSQ contained 20-items spread across three Clusters 'A and B.' Cluster 'A' elicits information on fringe benefits with 10-items and Cluster 'B' elicits information on recognition with 10-items. These items were placed on a 4-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA) (4 points), Agree (A) (3 points), Disagree (D) (2 points) and Strongly Disagree (SD) (1 point). Teachers' Job Commitment Questionnaire (TJCQ) as structured by the researcher measured teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The instrument TJCQ has 20-items with a 4-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA) (4 points), Agree (A) (3 points), Disagree (D) (2 points) and Strongly Disagree (SD) (1 point).

The instruments (TSRRS and TCMRS) were subjected to face and construct validation. Face validation was done by three experts, two in Educational Management and one in Measurement and Evaluation, all in the Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus. The reliability of the instrument was established for the different clusters of the instrument as well as the entire instruments using Cronbach Alpha which yielded coefficient values of 0.82 for fringe benefits and 0.79 for recognition. The average coefficient values of 0.81 for TSSQ and 0.86 for TJCQ are considered highly reliable and suitable for the study.

The instruments were administered to the respondents by the researcher with the help of four research assistants who were briefed on how to administer and retrieve the instrument

from the sampled respondents. A period of five weeks was used for the administration and retrieval of the instruments. Thus, out of 330 copies of the instrument administered, 318(93%) of the instrument were correctly completed and returned, while 12(7%) were either misplaced or not correctly filled. Simple linear regression analysis was used to answer the research questions and test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. This statistical tool was used because the study tends to predict between quantitative independent variables and quantitative dependent variables. Often, the objective is to predict the value of an output variable (or response) based on the value of an input (or predictor) variable. The data collected was analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25. For Regression Correlation (r), + Sign = Positive Relationship and - Sign = Negative Relationship. The negative sign means a negative coefficient which indicates a negative prediction or correlation between variables, while a positive sign means a positive coefficient which indicates a positive prediction or correlation between variables.

For p-value when, Sig. (2-tailed) < .05: Reject H_0 and Accept H_1 and where Sig. (2-tailed) > .05: Do not reject H_0 . In taking decisions on the null hypotheses, if p-value is equal to or less (\leq) than significant value of 0.05, the null hypothesis was not upheld, but if p-value is greater than ($>$), the significant value of 0.05 the null hypotheses was upheld.

Results

Research Question 1: How do fringe benefits predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 1: Summary of simple regression analysis with fringe benefit as predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized β	Std. Dev. β	Standardized β
Constant	27.421	4.198	
Fringe Benefits	0.546	0.338	0.518
R	0.518		
R^2	0.423		
Adj. R^2	0.409		

The summary of the simple regression analysis as shown in Table 1 indicated that fringe benefits positively predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State as shown by the regression coefficient ($R = 0.518$). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 0.423 indicated that the explanatory power of the variable was moderately strong. This implies that 42% of the variations in teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State were accounted for by the variations in teachers' fringe benefits. The adjusted R^2 supported the claim of the R^2 with a value of 0.409 indicating that 41% of the total variation in the dependent variable (teachers' job commitment) was explained by the independent variable (teachers' fringe benefits). Thus, adjusted R^2 supports the statement that the explanatory power of fringe benefits is moderately strong in determining the teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Nevertheless, the standardized beta weight ($\beta = 0.518$) showed that teachers' fringe benefits is a positive predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This implies that a unit increase in teachers' fringe benefits led to 0.513(51%) increase in teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Thus, the positive prediction of teachers' fringe benefits on their job commitment means that teachers'

job commitment moderately depends on the regular and prompt provision of fringe benefits to teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question 2: What is the predictive value of recognition on teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 2: Summary of simple regression analysis with recognition as predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized	Std. Dev.	Standardized
	β	β	β
Constant	25.271	4.615	
Recognition	0.532	0.367	0.504
R	0.504		
R ²	0.412		
Adj. R ²	0.397		

The summary of the simple regression analysis as shown in Table 2 indicated that recognition positively predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State as shown by the regression coefficient ($R = 0.504$). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 0.412 indicated that the explanatory power of the variable was moderately strong. This implies that 41% of the variations in teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State were accounted for by the variations in teachers' recognition. The adjusted R^2 supported the claim of the R^2 with a value of 0.397 indicating that 40% of the total variation in the dependent variable (teachers' job commitment) was explained by the independent variable (teachers' recognition). Thus, adjusted R^2 supports the statement that the explanatory power of recognition is moderately strong in determining the teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. More so, the standardized beta weight ($\beta = 0.504$) showed that teachers' recognition is a positive predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This implies that a unit improvement in teachers' recognition led to 0.504(50%) increase in teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Thus, the positive prediction of teachers' recognition on their job commitment means that teachers' job commitment moderately depends on the adequate provision of teachers' recognition and appreciation of teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Fringe benefits do not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 3: Test of significance of simple regression analysis with fringe benefits do not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized	Std. Dev.	Standardized	t-	p-
	B	β	β	value	value
Constant	27.421	4.198		23.641	0.000
Fringe Benefits	0.546	0.338	0.518	20.556	0.000
R	0.518				
R ²	0.423				
Adj. R ²	0.409				
F	35.125				0.000

The summary of the test of significance of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 3 showed that the simple regression coefficient (R) is 0.518 while the R^2 is 0.423 and Adjust R^2 is 0.409. The F-ratio associated with regression is 35.125, the t-test is 20.556 and the P-value = 0.000. Since p-value (0.000) is less than the specified level of significance 0.05, the study therefore rejected the null hypothesis that fringe benefits does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State and accepted the alternative hypothesis that fringe benefits significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Recognition does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 4: Test of significance of simple regression analysis with recognition does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized B	Std. Dev. β	Standardized β	t- value	p- value
Constant	25.271	4.615		22.975	0.000
Recognition	0.532	0.367	0.504	20.143	0.000
R	0.504				
R^2	0.412				
Adj. R^2	0.397				
F	30.427				0.000

The summary of the test of significance of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 4 showed that the simple regression coefficient (R) is 0.504 while the R^2 is 0.412 and Adjust R^2 is 0.397. The F-ratio associated with regression is 30.427, the t-test is 20.143 and the P-value = 0.000. Since p-value (0.000) is less than the specified level of significance 0.05, the study therefore rejected the null hypothesis that recognition does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State and accepted the alternative hypothesis that recognition significantly predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Discussion of the Findings

Findings on how fringe benefits predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State revealed that fringe benefits positively and significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. It is expected that all things being equal, teachers' job commitment should relate positively and significantly to adequate provision of fringe benefits to teachers in schools. The findings are as a result of teachers accepting the fact that provision of free transportation, subsidized professional development fees, scholarship to teachers' children, loans, wardrobe allowance, adequate accommodations, subsidized drugs, duty tour allowances paid, amenities provided and welfare packages are given to teachers' boost, encourage and motivate teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This finding is in agreement with the study of Chukwueze (2023) which found that fringe benefits are non-monetary motivators for teachers. Hence, the recognition of fringe benefits, beyond basic salaries, indicates an understanding of the broader spectrum of incentives that can enhance job satisfaction. Benefits such as healthcare, housing and other non-monetary perks contribute to a supportive work environment, influencing teachers' overall well-being and, consequently, their job performance. Sunoma *et al.* (2022) revealed that it is only when fringe benefits are regular

that teachers' job performance can be enhanced over time. Teachers can only show commitment to the school when they have the feeling that their needs are taken seriously. This is where regular payment of fringe benefits becomes very crucial. In addition to the salary paid to teachers, Aminu *et al.* (2023) opined that other financial entitlements like fringe benefits that come with the salary needs to be adequately provided as any shortfall in the payment of these financial entitlements can affect the commitment of teachers. Ifediorah-Okeke and Okaforcha (2019) noted that fringe benefits paid to the teachers therefore has a strong influence on the commitment of the teacher within and outside the school environment. Agah and Yakubu (2024) observed that fringe benefits have a positive and significant relationship with teachers' job performance. The similarity of the findings is as a result of using similar fringe benefits such school payment of hospital bills, provision of loan to teachers, availability of free accommodations and provision of free transportation among others. The use of fringe benefits as a support services is provided by school authorities to teachers in order to motivate them and boost their morale for better performance and achievement in schools. It can be deduced that most schools use fringe benefits as a reward for hard work and compensation system for teachers to get them satisfied with their job. More so, fringe benefits received by teachers are important for meeting other personal needs as they arise. When the teachers are not adequately motivated through fringe benefits, it affects other aspects of the teachers' life.

Findings on how recognition predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State revealed that recognition positively and significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. It is expected that all things being equal, teachers' job commitment should relate positively and significantly with teachers' recognition in schools. The findings are as a result of teachers accepting the fact that teachers; feel genuinely esteemed when management share with others their performance, have perception of unity in the school when there is show of gratitude from management, become more positive about teaching job when treasured by the school principal, are retained in school due to implementation of reward packages, feel fulfilled in the school when acknowledged with praises, recognition reinforce specific good behaviours, have greater passion for teaching job when management acknowledges their contributions to school, develop emotional connections to the workplace when recognized with their input, recognition build their self-esteem and recognition improve team culture. These findings are in line with the findings of Onaolapo *et al.* (2020) that teachers who receive regular recognition and praise are more likely to be productive, engaged, and satisfied with their work, which ultimately benefits their students and schools. Nwankwo and Francisca (2022) findings revealed that there is a very high positive and significant correlation among teachers' teamwork, job commitment and job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Quines and Nino (2023) suggested that recognition should be individualized and frequent and not limited to teachers' appreciation week. Ldama and Nasiru (2021) disclosed that recognition is so important because it meets a core human need for both the employee and the manager. Meeting this need is a key aspect of a strong company culture because it increases job satisfaction, employee engagement and retention, and quality of work. Kaegon and Okere (2023) found that recognition have high, positive and significant relationship with teachers' job commitment in public senior secondary schools. It was concluded that teachers are motivated to their job primarily by recognition and as such, if workplace practices are put in place there will be improved teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools. Recognition is not just about making teachers feel good, but it also has a significant impact on their performance and work engagement. It makes teachers feel valued and drives them to do their best in school.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the findings, the study concluded that provision of teachers' support services such as fringe benefits and recognition positively and significantly predicted teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Recommendations

The recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

1. Management and administrators of public secondary schools in Anambra State should as much as possible provide attractive and handy fringe benefits to create sense of loyalty and boost teachers' decisions to stay longer with their schools.
2. School principals should create a 'recognition-rich environment' in the school where praise comes from all directions on a daily basis to hard working teachers. This will motivate and boost the morale of teachers to put in their best in the profession.

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